

When a probability is assigned the value of 1

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This (very) short piece refers to the interesting *Kingfisherish Wandering* article on Mu Qi's 6 persimmons painting [1,2]. The article reflects a series of questions centering on the Buddhist monk painter's worldview and philosophy by examining the much-aspired painting.

Painting 1. Persimmons

The main workhorse for this little investigation is the [GITT-VT framework](#) [3].

Painting 2. Lao Zi [4]

This analytical approach involves the examination of possible assignments of probabilities to events of interest to the investigator.

Apparently, a probability assigned the value of 1 represents a certainty and thus aids our understanding of the value formation under [GITT-VT](#) [5].

By analyzing the infosphere and interactions of information provided by Painting 1, we reached our understanding of Mu Qi's Daoist philosophy, even though Mu Qi was a Buddhist monk, with quite a high likelihood, or usually stated in mathematical probability: "almost surely", or "a.s." But the probability of 1 is ideal.

Suddenly, I found Painting 2, also by Mu Qi.

This event gives us a probability of 1. And it also gives us another "a.s." event: Mu Qi used his Daoist view to draw a universe. Strikingly, he somehow figured out "a.s." that celestial planets have a spherical shape, long before modern physics confirmed this fact.

This is my moment of happiness since the question has been a conundrum for more than 8 years (maybe 9) after the painting was introduced by my artist friend, Bui Quang Khiem.

References

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[3] Vuong QH, La VP, Nguyen MH (2025) Bayesian probabilistic exploration of Bitcoin informational quanta and interactions under the GITT-VT paradigm. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2511.17646*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2511.17646>

[4] Zen Mesterek (nd) Muqi Fachang / Muxi Fachang (1210-1269). <https://terebess.hu/zen/mesterek/MuqiFachang.html>

[5] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH (2025) Developing Bayesian probabilistic reasoning capacity in HSS disciplines: Qualitative evaluation on bayesvl and BMF analytics for ECRs. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22987.86563>

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